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Emerging 5G and 6G Communication Systems

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Abstract

IMT- 2020 is the new mobile communication standard in force, known as 5G, which brought several improvements regarding latency, data capacity, simultaneous access and network sharing.

5G technology was conceived not as a standard, but the sum of several standards, making adjustments or changes possible, presented as some significant improvements in relation to its predecessor.

In this way, 5G was continually updated as we can see below, thus having "n" variations.

Currently, 5G technology is being implemented, but studies are already being carried out to determine the IMT-2030 framework, that is, 6G.

Figure 1: 3GPP - Initial 5G versions

This project aims to analyze these variations and modifications that occur in 5G, based on their implementations and the vision of the specialized market for these emerging technologies and try to determine whether the existing modifications are technology evolution or adaptations.

To achieve this objective, we will use the PRISMA methodology, to analyze between reports and seek contributions from market professionals on these variations and modifications.

Through a literary review of the reports, research evaluated using the methodology indicated above, carrying out a comparative analysis of the characteristics of 5G in light of the realities delivered in order to obtain a final report of the analyzes carried out.

Finally, we will seek to obtain an understanding of whether these variations are technological evolutions, adaptations or improvements.

Keywords: 5G, ITU-R, IMT- 2020, 3GPP, IMT-2030.

Resumo

IMT-2020 é o novo padrão de comunicação móvel em vigor, conhecido como 5G, o qual trouxe várias melhorias acerca de latência, capacidade de dados, acessos simultâneos e compartilhamento de rede.

A tecnologia 5G foi concebida não como um padrão, mas a somatória de diversos padrões, sendo assim possíveis de ajustes ou alterações apresentada como algumas melhorias sensíveis em relação a sua antecessora.

Dessa forma o 5G está sendo continuamente atualizado, conforme podemos perceber abaixo desde então "n" variações.

Atualmente estão ocorrendo as implantações da tecnologia 5G, mas já estão realizando os estudos para determinar o framework do IMT-2030, ou seja, o 6G.

Figura 1: 3GPP - versão inicial 5G

Este projeto visa analisar essas variações e modificações que ocorrem no 5G, baseados nas suas implementações e a visão do mercado especializado para essas tecnologias emergentes e tentar determinar se as modificações existentes são evolução da tecnologia ou adaptações.

Para alcançarmos esse objetivo utilizaremos da metodologia PRISMA, para assim analisar entre relatórios e buscando contribuições de profissionais de mercado sobre essas variações e modificações.

Mediante revisão literária dos relatórios, pesquisas avaliados utilizando a metodologia indicada acima, realizando uma análise comparativa das características do 5G em face das realidades entregues para assim obter um relatório final das análises realizadas.

Por fim, buscaremos obter um entendimento sobre se essas variações se são evoluções tecnológicas, adaptações ou melhorias.

Palavras-chave: 5G, ITU-R, IMT- 2020, 3GPP, IMT-2030.

1. Introduction

Emerging 5G and 6G mobile communication technologies are standards typically studied and validated by 3GPP [1], which are consolidated and presented by the ITU and thus adopted by the manufacturers in which operators will begin their implementations.

Figure 2: Requirements Triangle 5G

The fifth generation 5G R15 networks proposed: Massive Connectivity, Increased Capacity, Ultra High Reliability and Low Latency compared to its predecessor (4G) [2].

These networks, with their established characteristics, including operating frequency, capacity and pre-established services, determine a new market.

Actors (governments, manufacturers and operators) begin a new cycle of their products, current services (data and voice) and new ones provided by the new standard, in this case with IoT applications.

The complexity of these activities, regulations, implementations in the world of telecommunications to serve the entire market (B2B, B2C) and M2M of their networks so that they can have a standard of operation with their legacy network and with multiple equipment suppliers for users.

Therefore, your article is a description of the key points for 5G networks to meet service requirements, with an emphasis on new incorporated technologies, new network architectures and deployment scenarios [3].

After determining the standard and with the networks established, the validation of the standards and their pre-established functionalities by regulatory agencies/Institutes begins. With this, the real validation of protocols, capabilities and autonomy begins, which often does not behave as established.

In this way, organizations having constant interaction with manufacturers, with feedback on the performance of the adopted standard, begin to make adjustments and improvements to the standard, releasing new versions from time to time (figure 1).

These versions can often be simple adaptations, such as a sensitive variation that can actually be recognized by the market as a new version that will often cause interoperability and/or functioning problems with the already established network and/or with the devices in operation.

Before the 5G standard, variations brought performance or capacity improvements while maintaining the main characteristics.

As for 5G, this is what we will seek to discover, whether this standard was determined prematurely and is being consolidated with its implementations, resulting from feedback on its characteristics and performance.

As a result, 5G presents different aspects of implementation and variations in use, which may raise doubts about its standard [4].

However, the exponential growth in the number of applications and devices that depend on massive traffic exchange with other devices or the cloud, as well as applications that require real-time interaction, devices that work with artificial intelligence and automation, encounter some limitations in current mobile technology. . network technologies such as 5G. Sixth generation networks, or 6G networks, must meet the need for evolving key performance indicators (KPI) and expectations not met by the current generation [5].

As the main aspirations for the new architectures, we can mention the scope themes (URLC), driven by the optimization of fundamental technological technologies of Cloud, Deep Slicing, software and virtualization with an emphasis on network intelligence. Another important aspect is the ability of Deep Slicing to guarantee broad connectivity and service availability in terrestrial and non-terrestrial network coverage. [5].

This project aims to seek and map the edges that can systematically determine these issued variations, classifying them as adaptations (improvements to a defined standard) or evolution (new standard), thus having the possibility of proposing different suggestions on the evolution of the issued standards and /or questions about how to determine how these standards are established.

It is worth highlighting that as a secondary objective of this project, the result of this classification and analysis of emissions of 5G versions can validate that the new standard under study, that is, 6G, can be a variation of 5G, or it may indicate that this new standard can be issued along the same lines as the previous one.

2 Problem description

The mobile technology standards for the market are known as “xG” and new standards are delivered every decade.

When there was a need to launch 5G technology, as mentioned previously, a variation under study (Release 15) was adopted, which had the characteristics of figure 2.

We can see and it is part of this project to clarify whether this “maturity” was not sufficient or solid, as we have had several variations in the implementations of “5G”, and to date we are in the market evaluating and implementing new variations.

Thus, in this project using analysis of market institutes, positioning of manufacturers, as well as market research with experts as a knowledge base to consolidate the literary review.

This way we will be able to determine whether these variations are necessary adaptations that occurred with the implementations or actually modifications of the standard previously approved with 5G.

The proposed architectural models for 6G networks are still abstract for initial implementation [6].

Likewise, observing this reasoning, we seek to point out the understanding of the new standard to be proposed as a new model of the “G” family.

2.1 Objective

This work, within its limitations through the methodology used, seeks to answer the following question:

“5G technology is an adapted, modified system or an evolution.”

3.0 Methodology and Criteria

This project was prepared adopting the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic and Meta-Analysis - PRISMA methodology [7].

Initially, we defined what would be the object of this review in order to parameterize the research criteria to be carried out.

We used the IEEE Xplorer Digital library database as the main source, applying the determined filters and criteria, which will be demonstrated in item **3.2 - Criteria Applied to Research**.

Additionally, as sources of knowledge, we will be using data from institutes and/or companies recognized in the market, such as:

- Brazilian Market by Teleco Research;
- 5G European Observatory.

As a market view, we will carry out a survey with at least two experts about their view of emerging technologies in relation to the topic covered in this work.

3.1 Research Object

This report seeks to strictly answer the following question:

Are the promises of 5G: "Capacity Enhancement", "Massive Connectivity", "Ultra High Reliability" and "Low Latency" modifications, adaptations or evolutions of mobile system technology?

3.2 Criteria applied for Literary Review

Considering the PRISMA 2022 methodology, which is a guiding workflow, being flexible in defining the research method. In this way, we composed the modeling of the main library: IEEE Xplorer Digital.

Based on the question asked, we will adapt PRISMA so that we can create a primary flowchart in a traceable way. In which we will be applying the following initial filters:

Keyword	Constrain
Emerging 5G	OR
Emerging 6G	OR
Date Range (2018 - 2024)	AND
Report	AND

Table 1 - selection Criteria

After the initial filters, we only considered the roles considered in Magazine.

Therefore, we exclude papers in the following areas:

Edition	Quantity
Conference	1826
Journals	1034
Books	99
Early Access Articles	52
Standards	4

Table 2 - exclusion Criteria

From this variation, we will apply the filter individually:

KEYWORD	Filtro
Capacity Enhancement	ANALISYS
Massive Connectivity	ANALISYS
Ultra High Reliability	ANALISYS
Low Latency	ANALISYS

Table 3 - filter by area

In order to adjust the methodology to obtain the areas that may be material to respond to the object of this work, we will divide it into the following areas of study:

- Capacity Enhancement;
- Massive Connectivity;
- Ultra High Reliability;
- Low Latency.

Thus, we obtained the following studies by area to be eligible for primary literary review:

AREA	PAPERS
Capacity Enhancement	4
Massive Connectivity	23
Ultra High Reliability	30
Low Latency	193

Table 4 - papers by area

Due to the still high volume of papers in certain areas, we validated them to guarantee a minimum number of 4

and a maximum of 6 for each area.

Therefore, finalizing this composition of criteria and definitions so that we have reports by area of study in order to validate the issue that is the subject of this work.

Applying the selection limit we obtained the following quantities per area:

AREA	PAPERS
Capacity Enhancement	4
Massive Connectivity	6
Ultra High Reliability	6
Low Latency	6

Table 5 - numbers papers by area

In this way, we can demonstrate the complete flowchart of the literature that will be reviewed in figure 2:

Figure 2 - Complete PRISMA review flowchart

4 Literature review

As detailed in section **3.0 Methodology and Criteria**, the methodology applied and adapted as a selection, exclusion and filtering method generated 24 articles that we will separate by study area related to the objectives proposed for this work.

4.1 Capacity Enhancement

In the item proposed after segmentation and the process already explained, the item "Capacity Enhancement" generated 4 records in English obtained from the IEEE Xplore digital library.

The concept of ultra-dense networks is a new network model, in which its use has serious implications for ensuring the security of data and its users [8].

The Capacity Enhancement model allows for the probability of attack and subsequent invasion, its composition did not have a qualitative validation of its capacity x risks involved, thus making it necessary to develop vulnerability identification mechanisms, one of which is the temperature pattern [8].

When we see IoV - Internet of Vehicles, it has been one of the flagships of industrial development, given its potential. But, when we talk about "Capacity Enhancement" for IoV, this requirement promised by 5G, we note that we do not have a defined operational model [9].

This lack of definition of the service's behavior towards the network with the promise of "Capacity Enhancement", which with the use of autonomous cars, traffic control among other types of services caused by the IoT, specifically IoV, we realize that several items that guarantee this functionality of reliably are not established or functional [9].

Analyzing virtual reality services, in which 5G was considered "eXtend Reality" (XR), incorporating in this concept: virtual reality, augmented reality and mixed reality. In which its standard for operation requires a high level of connectivity and bandwidth used, due to the volume of simultaneous users, as well as the response time allowed must be minimal [10].

This service modality was introduced in 5G in its R17, in which the implemented model would enable XR applications, mainly cloud games, but we noticed that it generated errors and failures with the "Capacity Enhancement" when using the network, that is, its evolution in relation to the R15 standard has improvements to be validated and/or improved for the use of XR [10].

With this, "Capacity Enhancement" support, in this analysis of increased demand, limitations were investigated due to its modified standard R17 and thus enabling XR solutions, improvement is applied to validate and increase performance in the standard presented to the market, thus denoting a significant improvement for this requirement [10].

The concept of cells has been greatly developed since the LTE standard, ranging from micro cells to femto cells, with the centralized network signaling model now having a signaling overload with increased capacity, making a network complicated. [11].

This investigation applies the redesign of the architectural model using C RAN (Cloud Radio Access Network) with SDN (Software Define Network) to validate an improvement in performance capacity by decentralizing controls, thus bringing this application based on clouds to the edges. software [11].

The proposed modification shows an evolution of the standard, as it is no longer the model adapted from the previous standard for use in CDN and SDN with a new Frame, thus realizing an evolution of the 5G standard [11].

4.2 Massive Connectivity

In the item proposed after segmentation and process for the “Massive Connectivity” item, we chose 6 records in English obtained from the IEEE Xplore digital library.

mMTC - Massive Connectivity is a facet of the triangle of requirements proposed by 5G, and its focus is to provide massive connections, allowing “n” numbers of services and interactions, thus having low tolerance for delay, probably being one of the biggest offenders of throttling. from the Web [12].

One of the main problems that can occur in mMTC is the overload in network access, that is, due to this passive simultaneous connection [12], [16].

In the meantime, the congestion control mechanism in 5G, known as Extend Access Barring (EAB), was developed. [12].

In this way, the need for massive connections provided by the requirement for services to be provided by 5G adopted MIMO to significantly increase the number of connected devices and the bandwidth for the user [13], [14], [15].

This technology, which has been developed since R13 (pre-5G), in its current version brought the guarantee of delivery and reliability, but at the cost of complexity and energy use, and there is currently a proposal to improve this standard [13].

5G has been providing high demand for consumption and connections as predicted, and there are already developments regarding the use of MIMO technology, such as the NOMA standard, which provides improvements in performance and energy costs compared to the previous model [14].

The methods for controlling access in 5G (pull, push or paging) have some limitations, as they were originally designed to activate some devices on the network, and now the volume generates congestion or overload on the system [17].

4.3 Ultra High Reliability

In the item proposed after segmentation and process for the “Ultra High Reliability” item, we separated 6 records in English obtained from the IEEE Xplore digital library.

The structure to provide ultra-reliable latency communication (URLLC) and massive machine-type communication (mMTC) so that it can guarantee ultra high reliability through the beamforming used in the 5G standard has to be rethought [18].

The new applications that were announced with 5G constantly demand high performance and security capacity, in which new frameworks are necessary with network virtualization, in order to adjust the gap in existing equipment and/or available on the market [19].

The possibility of reducing costs, scalability and density, as well as dynamic network configuration for the use of fronthaul using 5G to replace traditional fiber backhaul brought new challenges, which are not entirely clear in the standard [20].

This theme demonstrates its innovation given the need to determine how to calculate or measure this requirement in mobile networks, as current methods do not consider all channel occupancy variables, such as wireless link, spatial diversity, channel occupancy, among others. parameters [21], [22].

The various applications, such as UAV, IoT will be viable with the determination of ultra high reliability standards, mainly for IoT scenarios, in which models are still being developed [23].

4.4 Low Latency

In the item proposed after segmentation and process for the “Low Latency” item, we separated 6 records in English obtained from the IEEE Xplore digital library.

5G supports three pillars, eMBB, mMTC and URLLC, and to validate all these pillars we have to consider low latency, thus being part of the 5G feasibility requirement structure for all service categories, network [18] , [19], [20], [21], [22], [23].

Latency permeates the entire composition of any element, network, connectivity, being highly sensitive for this architecture and services to operate, thus being a primary requirement for operation to be delivered by the 5G network [24].

Access and services in remote areas makes it a challenge to maintain latency at levels indicated by 5G, especially if the service requires a high volume of data and/or real time, and with new technologies there can be a great improvement in this aspect [25].

One of the approaches to minimize latency while maximizing the performance of the 5G system for services is virtualization, in this case mobile edge computing MEC, thus using a framework merging cloud computing with the access network [26].

Given the large differences in metrics for each network, Frame, equipment and services, a deeper analysis of the effective EC capacity is necessary to mathematically have the predictive model to effectively analyze the performance of each service, network of the 5G network [27].

As recommended and well seen on the topic, 5G architecture becomes a multi-varied technological challenge compared to its predecessors, with the low latency requirement increasingly becoming more difficult to achieve and thus new technologies are being developed [28].

Finally, we can observe that the complex 5G system demands different definitions of latency, making it necessary to define its contours for each part in order to adjust, apply, develop technologies, protocols to achieve performance improvements for each type. [29].

5 Market Analysis

5.1 Research Institutes and Companies

In the market study, we realized that the biggest offender for this work is the delays in implementation, which in some markets still lack regulation or authorization from the regulatory body and especially application in millimeter waves.

Therefore, market analyzes portray the stage at which the technology is being implemented.

5.1.1 Brazilian Market Research

In Brazil, the delay and release of licenses and regulatory problems on the subject have been delaying the implementation of 5G and thus all its promises of solutions and services.

When we analyze the Brazilian market, we realize that 5G has not yet made major advances, that is, it represents 7.46% of accesses, as we can see below: [30]

	Milhares	Novembro 2023
2G - GSM		20763
3G (WCDMA)		21038
4G - LTE		194060
5G - DSS		19020
Total		254881

Table 6: numbers mobile lines (fonte: www.teleco.com.br)

5.1.2 European 5G Observatory

When analyzing with the focus of the work proposed for the European 5G Observatory [31], we can first observe how 5G deployments behave in Europe and also in the main world markets.

	China	South Korea	Japan	USA	EU
Approximate number of 5G base stations	2,937,000	217,000	146,000	100,000	356,000
Total country population	1,425,700,000	51,800,000	123,300,000	334,000,000	448,400,000
5G base stations per 100,000 inhabitants	206	419	118	30	79
Indicative 5G subscribers	689,200,000	28,000,000	14,190,000	79,000,000	143,000,000
Indicative 5G subscribers per 100,000 inhabitants	48,341	54,054	11,509	23,653	31,891

Table 7: comparison of 5G rollout in international markets

In this analysis, it can be seen that 5G only in South Korea has more than 50% implementation, that is, the global market is still in the initial phase of implementation.

However, when we analyze the frequency spectrum being used by these markets, it becomes clear that 5G technology is not yet available for millimeter wave networks, which could result in several challenges arising from its implementation as an operation.

Figure 3 - Authorized 5G spectrum in international market

5.2 Survey with Market Experts

In the same way, but with a much more assertive focus on the topic of the work, the research below was carried out with at least two specialists in the cellular/telecommunications technology market, including operators and manufacturers.

The survey with three (3) experts using the following questionnaire yielded the following results:

Observing 5G deployments the requirements below:	Capacity Enhancement	Massive Connectivity	Ultra High Reliability	Low Latency
Update	2	1		1
Modification	-	-	-	-
Evolution	1	2	3	2

Table 8: research with the technology specialist

This research was objective without value judgment on the experts' opinion, thus providing a general value on each item questioned with the expert's own understanding.

6 Expected Results

The expectations for this project initially were to seek to understand and present the four characteristics of 5G and therefore why not design for 6G.

5G technology promises: Improved coverage, improved capacity, energy consumption, improved security and reduced costs.

Currently, 5G is already moving towards its R19 version, precisely to validate the triangle of services initially proposed.

However, focusing on the object of the work, we consider the following:

6.1 Capacity Enhancement

This requirement actually has an evolutionary proposal, given the services, networks and systems that will be necessary to provide it.

What we can see is that it is not yet fully implemented, even though 5G network installations are still being delivered.

We believe that even though it is a proposal for evolution, it is not yet consolidated, and for the focus of this work we have to realize that yes, it is an evolution, even if it is under construction.

6.2 Massive Connectivity

The solutions and adjustment of massive activation of devices already under study, using new approach techniques, make this item an item in constant evolution, which demonstrates adaptation in the initial composition of 5G.

"However, the legacy paging mechanism does not work well for mMTC, as it was originally designed for small-scale human-type communications [17]."

The proposed solutions may be promising, but they still require study and evolution[17].

Therefore, regarding the question object of this work, we can consider that regarding mTC the system has technology adaptations to provide service evolution.

6.3 Ultra High Reliability

New services, protocols and devices that demand a massive connection have been challenging the proposed model to guarantee the ultra high reliability proposal.

"To address such mismatches, several technological concepts like edge computing and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) have been adopted by 5G providers. [19]."

We can therefore understand that the evolution was proposed to be developed with the constant evolution of the 5G standard [19], [20].

Added to this statement is the need to determine how this requirement will be measured considering all the particularities of the mobile network. [21], [23].

Based on the literature, it can be observed that this requirement is an innovation to the point that there is still no framework, standard to determine its contours, and is therefore proposed and is in constant development with the implementation of networks and services in progress.

6.4 Low Latency

We separated this item, in order to demonstrate that latency in itself is not an innovation, low latency is a constant improvement of the technology, in other words, the quality of its delivery.

Validation of services is intrinsically viable the lower the 5G latency value is, and the more heterogeneous, dynamic, distance and massive occupancy, the greater the challenges will be to obtain the latency that can make the proposed service/network viable [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29].

Therefore, this requirement is clearly a proposed and mandatory improvement for the delivery of the proposed services to be permissible.

7 Conclusion

When we started this work, the biggest challenge was its construction and procedures, and over time it was adapted and improved.

We understand that this subject is vast and requires revisions, given the volume of existing reports that we had to separate to meet the deadlines.

Thus, in a restricted way, this topic, that is, 5G requirements, when asked whether they are evolution, adaptation or improvement, becomes very subjective when looking at the whole, that is, 5G is an evolution, as we noticed from the research of experts, but not from its requirements, but rather in the way of delivering this service network.

We can support this position, since until the previous network the focus was on network delivery so that we could validate services or new ones to be discovered.

With the advent of 5G, the services were already known and a system was created to support them.

I tend to conclude that 5G in terms of its requirements 6.1 is an evolutionary proposal, but items 6.2, 6.3, 6.4 are practically modifications and adaptations of existing solution networks, but it is a revolutionary approach, as they propose a new approach to network construction focused on the customer/service.

You could say that we don't have 5G, but rather the pre IAMN (mobile artificial intelligent network), as its challenges are focused on the new version which will be 6G but rather IIAMN.

8 References

- [1] 3 GPP GLOBAL INITIATIVE. "About 3GPP". Internet: <https://www.3gpp.org/about-us>, 2023. [Oct 04, 2023]
- [2] 3 GPP GLOBAL INITIATIVE. "Specifications & Technologies / Releases / Release15". Internet: <https://www.3gpp.org/specifications-technologies/releases/release-15>. Apr 26, 2019. [Oct, 20 2023]
- [3] IMT. "ITU-R Framework for IMT-2030". Internet: https://...IMT-2030_Framework_WP_5D_Management_Team.pdf. Jul, 2023. [Oct. 20, 2023]
- [4] Divya Jyothi V, Lavanya Srinivasachari. "2022 Dell Technologies Proven Professional Knowledge Sharing". Internet: https://education.dell.com/content/dam/dell-emc/documents/en-us/2022KS-Jyothi-5G_Challenges_Solutions_Future_Prospect.pdf. Em: Dell Inc. (2022). [Oct 15, 2023]
- [5] L. A. Oliveira, M. S. Alencar e W. T. A. Lopes. "Evolução da Arquitetura de Redes Móveis Rumo ao 5Gs". Em: pp 43-50 (ver p.1)
- [6] NETO, Heitor Scalco, et al. Uma visão de arquitetura para redes 6g. In: *Anais do I Workshop de Redes 6G*. SBC, 2021. p. 31-36.
- [7] PRISMA STATEMENT. "Prisma Framework". Internet : <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>. 2023. [Oct, 25 2023]
- [8] G. Chopra, R. K. Jha and S. Jain, "TPA: Prediction of Spoofing Attack Using Thermal Pattern Analysis in Ultra Dense Network for High Speed Handover Scenario," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 66268-66284, 2018, [doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2875921](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2018.2875921).
- [9] B. Ji *et al.*, "Relay Cooperative Transmission Algorithms for IoV Under Aggregated Interference," in *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 23, no. 7, pp. 9712-9725, July 2022, [doi: 10.1109/TITS.2021.3106545](https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2021.3106545).
- [10] P. Paymard, A. Amiri, T. E. Kolding and K. I. Pedersen, "Enhanced CQI to Boost the Performance of 5G-Advanced XR With Code Block Group Transmissions," in *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, [doi: 10.1109/TVT.2023.3333403](https://doi.org/10.1109/TVT.2023.3333403).
- [11] A. Rafiq, M. Afaq and W. -C. Song, "Mobility Performance Enhancement in Small Cells Cluster of 5G Network: A Handover Overhead Reduction Approach," *2020 21st Asia-Pacific Network Operations and Management Symposium (APNOMS)*, Daegu, Korea (South), 2020, pp. 373-376, [doi: 10.23919/APNOMS50412.2020.9236961](https://doi.org/10.23919/APNOMS50412.2020.9236961).
- [12] J. -R. Vidal, L. Tello-Oquendo, V. Pla and L. Guijarro, "Performance Study and Enhancement of Access Barring for Massive Machine-Type Communications," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 63745-63759, 2019, [doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2917618](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2917618).
- [13] W. A. Al-Hussaibi and F. H. Ali, "Efficient User Clustering, Receive Antenna Selection, and Power Allocation Algorithms for Massive MIMO-NOMA Systems," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 31865-31882, 2019, [doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2902331](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2902331).
- [14] M. R. Amini and M. W. Baidas, "Performance Analysis of URLL Random-Access NOMA-Enabled IoT Networks with Short Packet and Diversity Transmissions," *2020 International Conference on*

- Communications, Signal Processing, and their Applications (ICCSPA)*, Sharjah, United Arab Emirates, 2021, pp. 1-6, [doi: 10.1109/ICCSPA49915.2021.9385747](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCSPA49915.2021.9385747).
- [15] M. Bhuvaneswari and S. SasiPriya, "Performance Analysis of Various Techniques Adopted in a 5G Communication Network with a Massive MIMO System," *2020 International Conference on Inventive Computation Technologies (ICICT)*, Coimbatore, India, 2020, pp. 283-286, [doi: 10.1109/ICICT48043.2020.9112446](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICICT48043.2020.9112446).
- [16] B. Patnaik, A. Agarwal, S. Mali, G. Misra and K. Agarwal, "A Review on Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access Technique for Emerging 5G Networks and Beyond," *2020 International Conference on Smart Electronics and Communication (ICOSEC)*, Trichy, India, 2020, pp. 698-703, [doi: 10.1109/ICOSEC49089.2020.9215412](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICOSEC49089.2020.9215412).
- [17] W. Cao, A. Dytso, G. Feng, H. V. Poor and Z. Chen, "Differentiated Service-Aware Group Paging for Massive Machine-Type Communication," in *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 66, no. 11, pp. 5444-5456, Nov. 2018, [doi: 10.1109/TCOMM.2018.2848940](https://doi.org/10.1109/TCOMM.2018.2848940).
- [18] R. Li, H. Yan and D. Cabric, "Rainbow-Link: Beam-Alignment-Free and Grant-Free mmW Multiple Access Using True-Time-Delay Array," in *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 40, no. 5, pp. 1692-1705, May 2022, [doi: 10.1109/JSAC.2022.3143261](https://doi.org/10.1109/JSAC.2022.3143261).
- [19] G. Budigiri, C. Baumann, J. T. Mühlberg, E. Truyen and W. Joosen, "Network Policies in Kubernetes: Performance Evaluation and Security Analysis," *2021 Joint European Conference on Networks and Communications & 6G Summit (EuCNC/6G Summit)*, Porto, Portugal, 2021, pp. 407-412, [doi: 10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit51104.2021.9482526](https://doi.org/10.1109/EuCNC/6GSummit51104.2021.9482526).
- [20] J. Cezanne et al., "Design of Wireless Fronthaul With mmWave LOS-MIMO and Sample-Level Coding for O-RAN and Beyond 5G Systems," in *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 4, pp. 1893-1912, 2023, [doi: 10.1109/OJCOMS.2023.3308713](https://doi.org/10.1109/OJCOMS.2023.3308713).
- [21] I. A. M. Balapuwaduge and F. Y. Li, "A Joint Time-Space Domain Analysis for Ultra-Reliable Communication in 5G Networks," *2018 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC)*, Kansas City, MO, USA, 2018, pp. 1-6, [doi: 10.1109/ICC.2018.8422742](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICC.2018.8422742).
- [22] P. C. F. Eggers, M. Angjelichinoski and P. Popovski, "Wireless Channel Modeling Perspectives for Ultra-Reliable Communications," in *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 2229-2243, April 2019, [doi: 10.1109/TWC.2019.2901788](https://doi.org/10.1109/TWC.2019.2901788).
- [23] H. -M. Chen et al., "Resource Scheduling Algorithm for Delay Sensitive Service in IoT Scenarios," *2023 IEEE 98th Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC2023-Fall)*, Hong Kong, Hong Kong, 2023, pp. 1-6, [doi: 10.1109/VTC2023-Fall60731.2023.10333814](https://doi.org/10.1109/VTC2023-Fall60731.2023.10333814).
- [24] O. S. Al-Heety, Z. Zakaria, M. Ismail, M. M. Shakir, S. Alani and H. Alsariera, "A Comprehensive Survey: Benefits, Services, Recent Works, Challenges, Security, and Use Cases for SDN-VANET," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 91028-91047, 2020, [doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2992580](https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.2992580).
- [25] R. Abozariba, E. Davies, M. Broadbent and N. Race, "Evaluating the Real-World Performance of 5G Fixed Wireless Broadband in Rural Areas," *2019 IEEE 2nd 5G World Forum (5GWF)*, Dresden, Germany, 2019, pp. 465-470, [doi: 10.1109/5GWF.2019.8911655](https://doi.org/10.1109/5GWF.2019.8911655).

- [26] A. Akman et al., "5GMEDE - 5G Mobile Edge Computing with Enriched Radio Network Information Services," 2020 IEEE 25th International Workshop on Computer Aided Modeling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD), Pisa, Italy, 2020, pp. 1-5, [doi: 10.1109/CAMAD50429.2020.9209310](https://doi.org/10.1109/CAMAD50429.2020.9209310).
- [27] M. Amjad, L. Musavian and M. H. Rehmani, "Effective Capacity in Wireless Networks: A Comprehensive Survey," in IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 3007-3038, Fourthquarter 2019, [doi: 10.1109/COMST.2019.2929001](https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2019.2929001).
- [28] P. C. Gadge, S. S. Panda and P. Kumar, "A Survey on the Progressing 5G(NR) Modern Technologies and their Challenges," 2021 International Conference on Computing, Communication, and Intelligent Systems (ICCCIS), Greater Noida, India, 2021, pp. 834-839, [doi: 10.1109/ICCCIS51004.2021.9397090](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCCIS51004.2021.9397090).
- [29] M. Indoonundon and T. P. Fowdur, "Latency Components and Analysis in 5G New Radio," 2022 4th International Conference on Emerging Trends in Electrical, Electronic and Communications Engineering (ELECOM), Mauritius, 2022, pp. 1-8, [doi: 10.1109/ELECOM54934.2022.9965239](https://doi.org/10.1109/ELECOM54934.2022.9965239).
- [30] TELECO. "Estatísticas de celulares no Brasil". Internet: <https://www.teleco.com.br/ncel.asp> Dec 29th 2023. [Jan, 2024]
- [31] European 5G Observatory. "Interactive 5G Scoreboard". Internet: <https://5gobservatory.eu/observatory-overview/interactive-5g-scoreboard/> Jul 2023. [Jan, 2024].